

Title: does websearching provide ‘hints’ to studies overlooked by bibliographic database searching?

Background: In a previous case study,¹ the effect of geographic location on websearches using Google.com was assessed. In this case study, the effectiveness of the websearches from the previous case study were examined. The lens for this examination was the idea presented by Eynsenbach *et al.* that a contribution of websearching may be to examine hints to eligible studies if not the studies themselves.

Research aim: To explore the contribution of hints in web-searching: namely, are hints to studies frequent and do they help identify studies missed by bibliographic database searching?

A hint was defined as a link leading to identification of a relevant item.

Methods: All websearch results from the previous case study were assessed by the author to a predefined screening criterion. Eligible items were either studies or systematic reviews and these were categorised as either primary reports or hints. Three comparisons were made in analysis:

1. The prevalence of hints to primary reports;
2. The incidence of where a hint would have been necessary to identify the primary report based only on websearches in the original case study; and
3. The incidence of a hint where the primary report was not available in MEDLINE, Embase or The Cochrane Library.

Findings: Ten items fulfilled inclusion. These related to two studies and three systematic reviews. Seven hints compared to three primary reports were identified. All studies and two systematic reviews were available for retrieval in core bibliographic databases. It is possible that the systematic review not indexed in core databases (Pavey *et al.*) would be identified by a hint.

Conclusion: It was not possible to determine the importance of hints based on the sampling frame used in the previous case study but a role for hints is perceived in Health Technology Assessment, in particular to identify conference proceedings. With the pivot to on-line only conferences this may be valuable to test further.

The websearches identified no studies uniquely. For searchers located outside of the UK, it is possible that the primary report of a systematic review by Pavey would have been missed by websearches, but they would have identified a copy of this review, so this finding is unremarkable.

The finding that websearches identified no unique studies or systematic reviews aligned with prior expectation since it is anticipated that studies/reviews would be identified by bibliographic database searching in systematic reviews of medicine or Health Technology Assessment.

¹ Cooper, Chris, Theo Lorenc, and Ute Schauburger. "What You See Depends on Where You Sit: The Effect of Geographical Location on Web-Searching for Systematic Reviews: A Case Study." *Research Synthesis Methods* <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1485>

Background

Guidance indicates that searches of the internet should form part of a composite search for studies and study data when undertaking a systematic review.^{1,2} What is unclear, because there is limited guidance on the purpose and limited empirical evaluation of the effect, is what searches of the internet might contribute to the process of study identification in systematic reviews, beyond searches of bibliographic databases.³⁻⁵

In 2001, Eynsenbach *et al.* suggested that one contribution of websearching might be to identify ‘hints’ to on-going or recently completed studies which might be missed by traditional search methods, such as searching bibliographic databases.³ A hint might be a link or reference to identification of an unpublished or on-going study, or study data found on a website.³

Twenty years have passed since Eynsenbach *et al.* published their work. Through secondary analysis of an existing data set (described below), this paper re-examines the concept of hints.

Aim: To explore the contribution of hints in web-searching: namely, are hints to studies frequent and do they help identify studies missed by bibliographic database searching?

Methods:

This case study presents a post-hoc analysis of searches from a previous case study.⁴ The previous case study examined the effect of geographical location on websearch results by searching for the same medicine (Dasatinib) in 12 different countries.

Searching

Google.com was searched on Monday September 28, 2020 using Google Chrome (version 85.0.4183.121). A PC (Windows 10, 64-bit), using a virtual private network (SurfShark with an extension for Google Chrome (version 2.1.4)), was used to perform the searches by selecting servers in 12 different countries and performing the same search strategy each time.

Screening

The search results were screened by the author based on the inclusion criteria reported in Figure 1 but without restriction on date. The unit of interest was published/unpublished studies reporting randomised trials or systematic reviews of randomised trials.

Analysis

Eligible items were coded as primary reports or hints to primary reports.

A ‘primary report’ was defined as the original report of a study or a systematic review based on our original search results. For instance, a study published in a peer-reviewed journal (e.g. Cortes 2016 reported in the journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology)⁶ or a systematic review available as published report (e.g. Pavey 2014 as reported in the NIHR journal library).⁷ The phrase ‘primary reports’ is used to refer to both of the above examples in this study (i.e. studies or systematic reviews) NB: the study report classified as the primary study report in this case study may not be the primary report of that particular study overall. The examination here focuses only on the websearch results of the previous case study.

A ‘hint’ was defined as a an item identified which could lead to identification of an eligible primary report. For instance, a hint might be identification of eligible study via a Research Gate profile (e.g. Radich 2012)⁸ or identifying a systematic review by finding the technical

annex via a websearch (e.g. where Pavey 2014 was identified by the annex of search results).⁹ Hints would be extremely valuable if they identified a primary report not identified by another search method.

The following comparisons were made:

1. **The prevalence of hints to primary reports.** The comparison was between the number of hints compared to the availability of primary reports. The purpose of this comparison was not only to identify data on the prevalence of hints compared to primary reports but also the number of hints, assuming that, whilst there can only be one primary report, there might be multiple hints to that primary report.
2. **The incidence of where a hint would have been necessary to identify the primary report based only on websearches in the original case study.** This was assessed by splitting primary reports of studies from primary reports of systematic reviews. We also examined this by country, using the 12 countries from the original search, to see if any items were identified solely by hints in one country compared to primary reports in another.
3. **The incidence of a hint where the primary report would not have been identified by bibliographic database searching.** All eligible items were checked to determine if they were available for retrieval in the bibliographic databases listed below. These databases were chosen based on the guidance of the Cochrane Handbook.¹⁰ If items were not available in a database, we assumed that - in this study - the hint would be necessary to identify the item since otherwise we expected the items would have been identified in bibliographic searching. The following databases were searched:
 - MEDLINE (MEDALL) Ovid Interface: 1946 to May 10, 2021
 - Embase Ovid Interface: 1980 to 2021 Week 18
 - Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL). Wiley interface: Issue 4 of 12, April 2021
 - Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR). Wiley interface: Issue 4 of 12, April 2021

Findings

Forty-three (43) items were identified in total from the 12 countries searched. Of the 43 items, 10 items fulfilled inclusion. These related to two studies and three systematic reviews (see Table 1).

Table 1: findings of the three study comparisons

Item type & ID	Versions identified	Missed in any countries based on websearching	Primary report in databases
Study Radich 2012	Primary report: None	Missed in all countries.	Yes
	Hint: 1. PubMed Abstract of the study reported in the journal, <i>Blood</i> . ¹¹ 2. ResearchGate profile for the published study. ⁸	No. Both were identified in all countries.	
Study Cortes 2016	Primary report: 1. Study reported on journal web-page (<i>Journal of Clinical Oncology</i>). ⁶	Missed in 2 (of 12) countries: Canada and USA	Yes
	Hint: 2. Bibliographic record from PubMed. ¹²	Missed in 10 (of 12) countries: Australia; France; Germany; India; Italy; Japan; South Korea; Spain; Sweden; UK.	
Systematic review Douxflis 2016	Primary report: Review reported on journal web-page (<i>JAMA Oncology</i>). ¹³	Missed in 2 (of 12) countries: UK and USA	MEDLINE only
	Hint: web-page linking to the PDF annex of the review. ¹⁴	No. Identified in all countries.	
Systematic review Pavey 2014	Primary report Link to PDF download of the NIHR library version of the review. ⁷	Missed in 11 (of 12) countries: Australia; Canada; France; Germany; India; Italy; Japan; South Korea; Spain; Sweden; and USA	No
	Hint University of Queensland repository version; and ¹⁵ Link to PDF download of the technical annex to item 14. ⁹	No. Identified in all countries.	
Systematic review Tang 2019	Primary report: None	Missed in all countries.	MEDLINE and Embase
	Hint Link to the PDF version of the published review reported in <i>BMC Cancer</i> . ¹⁶	Missed in 1 (of 12) countries: Germany.	

Comparison 1: the prevalence of hints to primary reports

Seven hints (three to studies and four to reviews) compared to three primary reports (one to a study and two to reviews) were identified. This indicates that the number of hints was higher than the number of primary reports. In some cases there were multiple hints to a primary report.

Comparison 2: the incidence of where a hint would have been necessary to identify the primary report based only on websearches in the original case study.

On the basis of the websearches in the original case study, two studies fulfilled inclusion:

- The primary report of the study by Radich was not identified in any of the 12 countries searched. The study was identified by two hints in each of the countries searched. In this comparison, the hint would be necessary to identify the eligible study.
- The primary report of Cortes was identified in 10 of the countries searched but missed in Canada and USA. The hint would have identified the primary report in Canada and USA, but the hint was missed in the other 10 countries.

On the basis of the websearches in the original case study, three systematic reviews fulfilled inclusion:

- The primary report of Douxfils was identified in 10 countries but missed in the UK and USA. The hint was identified in all countries searched, meaning that the hint would be necessary to identify the review in the UK and USA.
- The primary report of Pavey was identified only in the UK. Otherwise the two hints, identified in all countries, would be necessary to identify the primary report.
- The primary report of Tang was not identified in any of the countries searched. The hint was missed in Germany, meaning that it was missed overall in Germany for this comparison, but identified by hints in the 11 other countries searched.

Comparison 3: The incidence of a hint where the primary report would not have been identified by a bibliographic database searching.

All of the studies identified as primary reports or by hints in websearching were also available for identification in bibliographic databases. We would anticipate that the study reports identified by websearching in this case study would already have been identified by searching bibliographic database in a full systematic review.

The review by Douxfils was available in MEDLINE and the review by Tang was available in MEDLINE and Embase. We would expect searches for a systematic review to search at least MEDLINE, so that these study reports would be identified by bibliographic database searching.

The review by Pavey was not indexed in any of the core bibliographic databases usually searched for a review of intervention effectiveness.⁷ The primary report of Pavey was only identified in the UK.⁷ Accordingly, in all other 11 countries, hints would be necessary to identify either a copy of the primary report (reported in the university of Queensland repository and identified in all 12 countries) or the technical annex of the original review via a PDF leading to identification of the primary report.

Discussion

This brief study focuses on the re-analysis of websearch results from a previous case study. It finds that hints to eligible study reports were frequent, often with multiple hints to a single primary report. This might be a reassuring finding as it suggests that eligible studies in the case study were unlikely to be missed since multiple reports/hints were identified. This finding must be contrasted with the resources required to process websearch results, since the findings indicate a screening burden which was assessed without identifying unique studies/reviews in this case study.³

As comparison 3 identifies, all study reports identified by websearches in the original case study were available for identification in leading bibliographic databases. We would anticipate that these study reports would be identified by a bibliographic database search in a real systematic review, making our findings here unremarkable. If a hint to a study were identified, which was not indexed in databases, this would be a more serious/interesting finding.

Hints *may* have been needed to identify the primary report of the 2014 systematic review by Pavey *et al.* if the researcher were based outside of the UK.⁷ The Pavey review does raise a question about hints, since researchers would have identified a copy of the review via the University of Queensland Repository (identified in all 12 countries – and where Dr Pavey now works). It begs the question, to what extent is this actually a hint, or simply an alternative version of the review.² The differences between pre/post publication, in particular changes made during peer-review, is an area of emerging interest.^{17,18} Further guidance on checking primary study reports to alternative versions of the same report might be useful. It may also be helpful to define what ‘hints’ mean in 2021, especially since they were not explicitly defined/categorised by Eysenbach *et al.*

The original case study only sought to evaluate the effect of geographic location. In analysing the role of hints in this case study, we do also explore the effectiveness findings from the original case study. The findings are unremarkable which was anticipated. This is because the way in which we used websearching was aligned to our specific research aim in the previous case study. It is not how searchers/researchers actually search for Health Technology Assessment (HTA) at this time.

We do still perceive value in using websearches to identify hints in HTA. One example might be to identify newly published conference abstracts or posters (although we did not find any in this sample). This is because there is some evidence (albeit it from a single case study) that the coverage of conference data is incomplete in bibliographic databases, notably Embase or Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science (CPCI-S).¹⁹ Social networking sites, like ResearchGate, can include conference presentations and so might offer hints in the Eysenbach *et al.* sense. This may be more important now (in 2021) given the number of conferences which have pivoted to on-line only during the COVID pandemic. Furthermore, targeted or iterative websearches are used as specific search enquiries, namely to identify

² It is noted that the Pavey review is indexed in the HTA database hosted by the Centre for Reviews and Dissemination (University of York) but it is unclear how commonly this resource is searched now, since it has not been updated since 2015 (Pavey was published in 2014, hence it is available for retrieval).

specific data for a report (e.g. incidence of a condition) or to identify values for a decision-analytic model (local cost of medicines).

The role of websearching in systematic reviews and other forms of synthesis remains an area of active interest. The focus of our future work is to examine how to harness the findings of the original case study and to better examine the role of hints in a correctly designed study. As we report in the original case study, we perceive that the variation identified by geographic location could be used to an advantage. For example, once a clear list of studies have been identified using traditional search methods, secondary searches could be undertaken. These searches would focus on the name of the study (for instance) and, if the study was conducted in a specific country or countries, the virtual private network approach used in the case study could be used to search for unpublished data or hints (e.g. evaluation reports, sibling qualitative data etc.). We anticipate that this approach would be particularly valuable for reviews of complex interventions. A rough conceptualisation is illustrated in Figure 2. A process model is being developed as this idea is further examined by the authors of the previous case study.

Limitations

- This is a post-hoc analysis of data gathered for another research aim.
- The searches are specific to the research aim of the previous case study. We have not compared the websearches to other search methods by undertaking further searches, so we are unable to comment on the sensitivity of the websearches and completeness of the sample.
- Search results were screened by one researcher, not two.
- The findings are specific to this analysis and cannot necessarily be generalised to other reviews or contexts.

Conclusion

This study presents a secondary analysis of websearch results from a previous case study.

The research aim of this study was to examine the search returns from the previous case study. In particular, to explore the role of hints in identifying primary reports, and to assess if studies or systematic reviews identified in the websearches would also have been identified by bibliographic database searching.

It was not possible to determine the importance of hints based on the sampling frame used. A role for hints is still perceived in Health Technology Assessment, in particular to identify conference presentations, but no evidence to support this idea was identified. With the pivot to on-line only conferences this may be valuable to test further.

The websearches identified no studies uniquely. For searchers located outside of the UK, it is possible that the primary report of a systematic review by Pavey would have been missed by websearches, but they would have identified a copy of this review, so this finding is unremarkable.

In general, the finding that websearches identified no unique studies or systematic reviews aligned with prior expectation since it is anticipated that studies/reviews would be identified by bibliographic database searching in systematic reviews of medicine or Health Technology Assessment.

Figure 1: Screening criteria from Pavey *et al.*⁷

For the review of clinical effectiveness, in the first instance, only systematic reviews of randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and RCTs were considered. However, if key outcomes of interest were not measured at all in the included RCTs we discussed whether extending the range of included studies to other study designs. Other study designs were not required after scrutiny of the included RCTs.

The systematic reviews were used as a source for finding further studies and to compare with our systematic review. Systematic reviews provided as part of manufacturers' submissions were treated in a similar manner.

Population: Adults with chronic phase CML, naïve to any treatment specifically directed against CML

Interventions: Dasatinib Nilotinib Imatinib (400mg standard dose) Each should be employed in accordance with the marketing authorisation and in the populations indicated in Section 2.6, noting that CML without genetic mutation is outside the existing marketing authorisations.

Comparators: Imatinib or nilotinib where the intervention is dasatinib; imatinib or dasatinib where the intervention is nilotinib; dasatinib or nilotinib, where the intervention is standard dose imatinib.

Outcomes: All potentially relevant outcomes in the included studies were considered, particularly those capturing:

- Response rates –cytogenetic, molecular and haematological;
- Event-free survival;
- Progression-free survival;
- Time to progression;
- Overall survival;
- Time to treatment failure;
- Adverse effects of treatment; and
- Health-related quality of life.

NB: no date limit was applied for screening websearches which means the inclusion criteria above was applied for any study or systematic review to 28 September 2020.

Figure 2: brief conceptualisation on using websearches in complex systematic reviews.

Search 1 (the main searches: using A Conventional Approach)	Purpose
<p>Bibliographic databases Citation searching Handsearching etc.</p>	<p>The purpose of these searches is to identify studies and ideally all study reports of effectiveness data and or qualitative data (for example).</p> <p>This search should result in being able to list:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the names of studies and the geographic location of their study sites, • names of specific interventions, and • the names of the researchers/organisations involved.
Search 2 (secondary searching)	Purpose
<p>Websearching</p>	<p>Targeted websearching using the name of the study/studies, intervention sites, and researcher names/organisations.</p> <p>The purpose of this websearch is to identify published/unpublished study reports, evaluation studies, unpublished data sets, extended qualitative reports: anything relating to the studies/interventions which may not be traditionally reported.</p> <p>In further work, we are examining if using a VPN to search in the country where a specific study was conducted might help identify data which might be missed if the country of search is different. Our findings in the research note allude to this, since the Pavey <i>et al.</i> HTA report was more commonly identified by the report in the University of Queensland repository (where Dr Pavey works) than the NIHR HTA monograph published in the UK (where Pavey <i>et al.</i> conducted the review). This work is a work in progress.</p>

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